

4-Heterocyclic Amino- α -substituted *o*-Cresols. Part I. Synthesis of 9-(3'-Substituted Aminomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino)-acridine Derivatives

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2,7-Dimethoxy- and 2-methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloro-9-(3'-substituted aminomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino)-acridine derivatives have been synthesized. The UV spectra of these compounds have been studied.

Following the observation that α -dialkylamino-*o*-cresols possessed antimalarial properties, Burckhalter *et al.*, condensed 3-diethylaminomethyl-4-hydroxyaniline with 3-chloro-7-methoxy-9-chloroacridine to obtain an analogue of quinacrine and with 4,7-dichloroquinoline to obtain camoquine. Both these compounds have been reported as active antimalarials¹. The present communication deals with the synthesis of 2,7-dimethoxy- and 2-methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloro-9-(3'-substituted aminomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino) acridine derivatives by condensing the required 9-chloroacridine derivatives with a 3-substituted aminomethyl-4-hydroxyaniline.

2,7-Dimethoxy-9-chloroacridine (I) has been synthesised according to Kahatriya *et al.*² 2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8,9-dichloroacridine (II) has been synthesised by chloroacrylodehydration of 4-methoxy-2'-methyl-5'-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid with phosphorus oxychloride. The latter acid was formed on the Ullmann condensation of 2-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid with 2-methyl-5-chloroaniline. 2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8,9-dichloroacridine has been characterised by preparing its 9-phenoxy derivative.

9-(3'-Diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino) derivatives of 2,7-dimethoxy- and 2-methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloroacridines were formed on condensing compounds (I) and (II) with 3-diethylaminomethyl-4-hydroxyaniline in HCl solution. The substituted aniline used was not isolated as a free base or a hydrochloride. The reaction mixture (10% HCl solution) containing the hydrochloride of the base, obtained on hydrolysis of its *N*-acetyl

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1883; 1946, 68, 1894.
2. Burger, "Medicinal Chemistry", Vol. II, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1961, pp. 801, 804.
3. *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1946, 15A, 42; *Chem. Abs.*, 1947, 41, 6214.

derivative, was directly used for the condensation. Following this method, 3-piperidinoacridines and 3-morpholinomethyl-4-hydroxyanilines have been condensed with (I) and (II) to yield the corresponding 9-(3'-substituted aminomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino) acridine derivatives.

2,7-Dimethoxy-9-(3'-piperidinomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino)acridine and the corresponding 9-(3'-morpholinomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino)analogue have been synthesised by following an alternative method, involving the Mannich reaction of 2,7-dimethoxy-9-(*p*-hydroxyanilino)acridine (III) with paraformaldehyde and piperidine or morpholine, respectively. Compound (III) was prepared on condensing (I) with *p*-aminophenol in HCl solution. It was not possible, however, to synthesise 2,7-dimethoxy-9-(3'-diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino)acridine according to this procedure.

The electronic spectra of all the acridine derivatives, described here, have been studied in the region from 220 to 500 m μ on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer in exactly about 10⁻⁵ molar ethanolic solutions. Twice-distilled ethanol from all-glass apparatus was used as a solvent. The spectral data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Substituent.	β band.		Para band		λ_{max} .	Log ϵ .	λ_{max} .	Log ϵ .
		λ_{max} .	Log ϵ .	λ_{max} .	Log ϵ .				
1	2,7-Dimethoxy-9-chloro-	261 m μ	5.06	380 m μ	4.18				
2	2,7-Dimethoxy-9-phenoxy.	259	4.85	375	4.05				
3	2,7-Dimethoxy-9-(<i>p</i> -hydroxyanilino)-	262	4.75	377	3.98	490 m μ	3.97		
4	2,7-Dimethoxy-9-(R ₁)	259	4.75	378	4.02	435	4.02		
5	2,7-Dimethoxy-9-(R ₂)	265	4.75	376	3.99	430	3.97		
6	2,7-Dimethoxy-9-(R ₃)	259	4.75	376	3.96	430	3.98		
7	2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8,8-dichloro-	266	5.06	368	3.79	395	3.78	415 m μ	3.75
8	2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloro-9-phenoxy-	264	5.05	362	3.83	390	3.86	410	3.86
9	2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloro-9-(R ₁)	262	4.78	370	3.56	429	3.82		
10	2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloro-9-(R ₂)	262	4.76	370	3.71	431	3.88		
11	2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloro-9-(R ₃)	262	4.77	371	3.67	434	3.89		

N.B.-(R₁), (R₂), and (R₃) refer to 3'-diethylaminomethyl-, 3'-piperidionomethyl-, and 3'-morpholinomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino, respectively.

Spectra of the various 9-substituted anilino-2, 7-dimethoxyacridines resemble each other very closely with regard to the position, structure, and intensity of the constituent bands. The same type of close similarity has been observed in the spectra of the 9-substituted anilino-2-methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloroacridine derivatives. The spectra of 9-chloro-2,7-dimethoxyacridine and the corresponding 9-phenoxy derivative resemble each other, but differ from the spectra of the corresponding 9-anilinoacridine derivatives; the short wave-length band, the β band, in the spectrum of each of the former type of compounds is more intense and appears at longer wave length than the corresponding bands in the spectra of the 9-anilino-2,7-dimethoxyacridine derivatives. The long wave-length band,

the *para* band, in the spectra of the β -chloro- and β -phenoxy-2,7-dimethoxyacridines have no fine structure, whereas the similar band in the spectra of the corresponding θ -substituted anilino derivatives has a fine structure comprising two sub-bands.

The β -band in the spectra of 2-methoxy-6-methyl-8,9-dichloroacridine and its θ -phenoxy analogue is more intense than the corresponding band in the spectrum of θ -substituted anilinoacridine of the same series. This difference in the spectra of the θ -substituted anilino derivatives and the corresponding θ -chloro and θ -phenoxy derivatives may be held to support the formulation of θ -anilinoacridine as θ -phenyliminoacridan at least in solution. Such a formulation is in accordance with the observation of Turnbull⁴ and of Acheson *et al.*⁵ that a θ -aminoacridine exists in its solution in the θ -iminoacridan form.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Diethylaminomethyl-, 3-piperidinomethyl-, and 3-morpholinomethyl-4-hydroxyacetanilides required were synthesised, following the methods described in literature⁶. The anilide derivative was hydrolysed by heating it with HCl (dil.) and the reaction mixture containing the base in solution was directly used without isolating the amine.

2,7-Dimethoxy-9-(3'-piperidinomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino)acridine: Method A.—A mixture of 3-piperidinomethyl-4-hydroxyacetanilide (0.01*M*) and HCl (20 ml, 20%) was refluxed at 120-25° for 1 hr. The solution was rendered just acidic by adding the required amount of dilute alkali. To this solution 2,7-dimethoxy-9-chloroacridine (0.01*M*) was added and heating was continued on a boiling water bath for 2 hr. The solution was cooled and treated with a slight excess of ammonia to precipitate the base. It was collected, dried, and crystallised from ethanol in greenish yellow clusters of needles, m.p. 204-205°. (Found: N, 9.45. C₂₇H₂₉O₃N₄ requires N, 9.48%).

The *dihydrochloride*, formed as a yellowish brown solid, melted with decomposition at 247-48°. (Found: N, 8.32; equiv., 254. C₂₇H₃₁O₃N₃Cl₂ requires N, 8.14%; equiv., 258).

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1046, 441.

5. *Ibid.*, 1954, 3742.

6. D.R.P. 92, 309/1897; Friedländer, 1897, 4, 103.

2,7-Dimethoxy-9-(*p*-hydroxyanilino)acridine was prepared, as described above, by heating a reaction mixture of 2,7-dimethoxy-9-chloroacridine (2.5 g.) and *p*-aminophenol (1.09 g.) in 1*M*-HCl (20 ml) for 4 hr. It was crystallised from ethanol as a yellowish powder, m.p. 253-54°. (Found: N, 8.0. $C_{21}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.1%).

2,7-Dimethoxy-9-(3'-morpholinomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino)acridine: *Method B*.—To a solution of morpholine (0.01 *M*) in ethanol (20 ml) a mixture of 2,7-dimethoxy-9-(*p*-hydroxyanilino)acridine (0.01 *M*) and paraformaldehyde (0.01 *M*) was added in small lots with intermittent stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 5 hr. Excess solvent was removed by distillation and the residue was dissolved in a minimum amount of boiling acetone. The solid dihydrochloride, precipitated on treating the acetone extract with HCl, was collected and treated with ammonia solution. The base separating was crystallised from ethanol in greenish yellow needles, m.p. 230-31°. (Found: N, 9.20. $C_{26}H_{27}O_4N_3$ requires N, 9.44%).

The dihydrochloride, formed as a brown solid, melted with decomposition at 225-26°. (Found: N, 8.24; equiv., 256. $C_{26}H_{29}O_4N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 8.11%; equiv., 259).

2,7-Dimethoxy-9-(3'-diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino)acridine was formed by condensing 2,7-dimethoxy-9-chloroacridine with the hydrolysate of 3-diethylaminomethyl-4-hydroxyacetanilide, following method (A). It was crystallised from ethanol in greenish yellow needles, m.p. 202°. (Found: N, 9.95. $C_{26}H_{29}O_3N_3$ requires N, 9.75%).

The dihydrochloride, obtained as a greenish yellow powder, melted at 244-45° with decomposition. (Found: N, 8.1; equiv., 249. $C_{26}H_{31}O_4N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 8.33%; equiv., 252).

2'-Methyl-5'-chloro-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was obtained on condensing 2-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid (11.5 g.) with 2-methyl-5-chloroaniline (7.0 g.) and a trace of copper powder, using isoamyl alcohol (30 ml) as a solvent. It was crystallised from acetic acid in greenish needles, m.p. 169-70°, yield 11.0 g. (Found: N, 4.9; equiv., 289.0. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3NCl$ requires N, 4.8%; equiv., 291.5).

2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8,9-dichloroacridine was prepared on heating 2'-methyl-5'-chloro-4-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (10.0 g.) with $POCl_3$ (30 ml) at 110° for an hour. The solid product, obtained on diluting the cooled reaction mixture with a large excess of dry ether-petroleum, was stirred with an excess of ammonia solution, collected, washed, and dried in air. It was crystallised from chloroform in small yellow needles, m.p. 163-64°, yield 7.0 g. (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{15}H_{11}ONCl_2$ requires N, 4.8%).

2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloro-9-phenoxyacridine, formed on heating 2-methoxy-5-methyl-8,9-dichloroacridine with excess of phenol, was crystallised from ethanol in light brown small needles, m.p. 169°. (Found: N, 3.9. $C_{21}H_{16}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.0%).

2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloro-9-(3'-diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino)acridine, formed on condensing 2-methoxy-5-methyl-8,9-dichloroacridine with the hydrolysate of 3-diethylaminomethyl-4-hydroxyacetanilide, following method (A), was crystallised from ethanol as a reddish yellow powder, m.p. 97-98°. (Found: N, 9.1. $C_{26}H_{28}O_2N_3Cl$ requires N, 9.3%).

The *dihydrochloride* of this product could not be crystallised due to its slight hygroscopic nature. It was dried by heating it at 100°. The product thus treated melted at 158-59° with decomposition. (Found: N, 7.8; equiv., 258.0. $C_{26}H_{30}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 8.0%; equiv., 261.2).

2-Methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloro-9-(3'-piperidinomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino)acridine was prepared by condensing 2-methoxy-5-methyl-8, 9-dichloro-acridine with the 3-piperidino-methyl-4-hydroxyacetanilide hydrolysate. It was crystallised from acetone in orange plates, m.p. 164°. (Found: N, 9.3. $C_{27}H_{30}O_2N_3Cl$ requires N, 9.1%).

The *dihydrochloride*, obtained as an orange solid, melted with decomposition at 254-55°. (Found: N, 8.0; equiv., 269.0. $C_{27}H_{30}O_2N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 7.9%; equiv., 267.2).

The *morpholino analogue* of the preceding acridine was prepared by condensing 2-methoxy-5-methyl-8, 9-dichloro-acridine with the hydrolysate of 3-morpholinomethyl-4-hydroxyacetanilide, following method (A). It was crystallised from ethanol in orange plates, m.p. 156-57°. (Found: N, 9.2. $C_{26}H_{26}O_3N_3Cl$ requires N, 9.1%).

The *dihydrochloride*, obtained as a yellowish orange solid, melted at 251° with decomposition. (Found: N, 8.0; equiv., 268.0. $C_{26}H_{26}O_3N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 7.8%; equiv., 268.5).

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